

Occurrence of white tip disease in deepwater rice in Bangladesh

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Rice white tip disease, caused by the nematode *Aphelenchoides besseyi* Christie 1942, was reported near Dacca in 1955 but its distribution in other deepwater rice areas and the extent of crop and yield damage in Bangladesh are unknown. In 1981 white tip was found in the Manikganj, Narshingdi, and Chandina deepwater rice areas. Samples were taken at booting stage and examined for nematodes. About 60% of the rice fields in Manikganj were infested. New symptoms induced by this nematode and its influence on some plant characters including yield components were recorded.

Chlorotic discoloration on the leaf base just below the collar at 2- to 3-leaf stage of the seedling and splash patterned chlorosis or chlorotic stripes on the innermost leaf with a whitish tip at the elongating stage of the crop were disease symptoms. The flag leaf of the infected plant was shortened, twisted, crinkled, and often distorted or split longitudinally. The panicle emerged partially or completely and had whitish spikelets on the tip or throughout.

In a preliminary survey, the local deepwater rice variety Rajboalia was highly susceptible to white tip nematode. It was examined to assess nematode population in rice grains and influence on panicle length, panicle weight, and some yield components. Ten panicles with white tip symptoms and 10 healthy panicles were sampled from each of 10 different fields. Panicle length and weight were measured. Filled and sterile grains were counted, then grains were threshed and bulked separately. One thousand grains from each bulk sample were weighed and nematode population in 100 grains was estimated by soaking split grains overnight and examining and counting nematodes under a microscope.

Population density of white tip nematode in rice grains and its influence on panicle length, panicle weight, and yield components in deepwater rice variety Rajboalia, Bangladesh, 1981.

Character	Healthy plant	Diseased plant	Mean difference ^a
Nematode population/100 grains	112	650	538**
Panicle weight (g)	5.7	1.9	3.7**
Panicle length (cm)	30.0	23.0	7.0**
Filled grains/panicle	173	47	126**
Sterile grains/panicle (%)	21.8	77.2	55.4**
1,000-grain weight (g)	18.1	5.5	12.6**

^a**All differences are statistically significant (*t*-test) $p = 0.01$.

Panicles from plants with white tip symptoms were significantly shorter, weighed less, had fewer filled grains and

lower 1,000-grain weight. There were significantly more nematodes per 100 grains (see table).

In vitro toxicity of some fermented oil cake extracts to *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Sclerotium oryzae*

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Applying some nonedible oil cakes is thought to increase some soil antagonist populations. We studied the effect of oil cakes commonly used by Indian farmers on in vitro inhibition of *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Sclerotium oryzae*, which cause rice sheath blight and stem rot.

Two hundred grams each of kusum *Schleichera trijuga*; mohuwa *Bassia latifolia*; neem *Melia azadirachtae*; and sal *Schorea robusta* were placed in plastic mug and fermented for 25 days in irrigation water. Contents were then filtered and the supernatant was centrifuged. The resultant solution was adjusted to 200 ml stock solution by flash evaporation. The stock solution was added to potato dextrose agar (PDA) media in different concentrations (see table) and autoclaved. Nutrient concentration (potato decoction and glucose) for all

Growth inhibition of *R. solani* and *S. oryzae* in fermented oil cake extracts, Hyderabad, India.

Oil cake	Concentration		<i>R. solani</i> colony diameter (cm)	PI ^a	<i>S. oryzae</i> colony diameter (cm)	PI ^a
	Medium	Extract				
Kusum	180	20	3.8	57.7	1.4	72.7
	160	40	1.3	85.6	1.0	83.6
	140	60	0.8	91.1	0	100.0
	120	80	0	100.0	0	100.0
Mohuwa	180	20	4.6	48.9	1.1	80.0
	160	40	4.6	48.9	0.7	87.2
	140	60	4.3	53.3	0	100.0
	120	80	4.1	54.4	0	100.0
Neem	180	20	4.5	50.0	0	100.0
	160	40	2.8	69.0	0	100.0
	140	60	2.0	77.8	0	100.0
	120	80	0.8	100.0	0	100.0
Sal	180	20	3.4	62.2	3.9	29.1
	160	40	2.5	73.3	3.7	32.7
	140	60	0	100.0	3.1	45.5
	120	80	0	100.0	2.0	63.6
Control	Potato dextrose agar		9.0	—	5.5	—
	C.D. for colony diameter		0.31	C.D. for colony diameter	0.19	
	C.V.		7.76%	C.V.	10.35%	

^aPercentage of growth inhibition (PI) over check.